

Alexandros Balaskas, Joseph Merab, Carolina Diamandis
LCG Research, Kifisias Ave 16, 11526 Athens
diamandis@lazar-consortium.com

Metabolic and Cardiac Implications in Oshtoran Syndrome (H63D Syndrome Type-3): A Case Report

Abstract:

This report highlights the complex interplay between cardiac function, metabolic disorders, and the impact of Oshtoran Syndrome on overall health. Particular emphasis is placed on the implications of a left ventricular ejection fraction (LV-EF) decline, PDH cytopathy, and the resultant metabolic dysregulation. Additionally, the critical role of catecholamine suppression in preventing potentially life-threatening episodes is discussed.

Introduction:

Oshtoran Syndrome (H63D Syndrome Type-3) presents a multifaceted clinical challenge, characterized by both cardiac and metabolic complications. This report examines the deterioration in cardiac function, the metabolic impact of PDH cytopathy, and the systemic effects observed in a patient with this syndrome, along with the essential role of catecholamine suppression.^{1,4,5}

Cardiac issues:

Left Ventricular Ejection Fraction (LV-EF): The patient's LV-EF has decreased from 63% to 49%, indicating a significant impairment in the heart's ability to pump blood and oxygen efficiently. This decline reflects a compromised cardiac function, likely contributing to systemic hypoperfusion and metabolic stress.^{9,10,11,12}

Left Bundle Branch Block (LBBB)

Initially, the LBBB was pulse-dependent, manifesting only at elevated pulse rates. Over a period of five months, the pulse threshold for the occurrence of LBBB gradually decreased,

eventually leading to a persistent block irrespective of heart rate. This progression suggests a deteriorating condition in the cardiac conduction pathways.

Metabolic Disorders

PDH Cytopathy: The patient exhibits a disorder in the pyruvate dehydrogenase complex (PDH), impairing the conversion of pyruvate to acetyl-CoA, a crucial step in ATP production. This metabolic dysfunction leads to increased lactate production and reduced ATP availability, contributing to inefficient cellular energy production.¹³

Anaerobic Metabolism

Due to the PDH cytopathy, the patient's body is forced to rely more on anaerobic metabolism, resulting in an accumulation of lactate rather than ATP. This inefficient pathway exacerbates metabolic stress and contributes to symptoms such as muscle fatigue, general malaise, and reduced physical and executive functioning.¹⁴

Lactate Levels and Energy Metabolism

Postprandial and Exercise-Induced Lactate Levels: The patient's lactate levels increase significantly after meals (up to 5 mmol/L) and after light physical activity (e.g., 20 push-ups, reaching 7-8 mmol/L). These elevated lactate levels indicate a severe energy deficit and impaired ATP production, reflecting the very complex underlying metabolic derangements.^{13,14}

Catecholamine Dysregulation

Autonomic Dysfunction causes unpredictable, unregulated catecholamine surges due to autonomic dysregulation. These surges significantly exacerbate metabolic issues, imposing additional stress on the energy metabolism and contributing to neuropsychiatric symptoms such as extreme fatigue and "narcoleptic" episodes. Anamnestically, the patient has been exhibiting signs of steatosis and pathological catecholamine regulation since his puberty, with these latter plus severe neuropsychiatric worsening following weight loss or dieting efforts. The subsequent exacerbation of neuropsychiatric symptoms post-weight loss indicates a correlation between metabolic stress and energy insufficiency. That means: the patient had signs of liver steatosis

(fatty liver) since adolescence, which have been exacerbated by periods of rapid weight loss and dieting. The unregulated catecholamine surges and metabolic disturbances, including PDH cytopathy, likely contribute to fluctuating levels of liver steatosis which has had along a Focal Nodular Hyperplasia (FNH).^{4,5,6,15,16}

Glucose issues, monitoring and management

The patient uses a modern glucose monitor that provides real-time graphical representation of glucose levels. This device helps identify plateau phases or glucose spikes without food intake, indicative of gluconeogenesis, prompting the need for immediate intervention. In cases of non-food-related glucose spikes, the patient should consume a small to moderate amount of rapidly available carbohydrates (e.g., dextrose tablets or a sugary drink) to stabilize blood glucose levels and prevent ATP decompensation.¹¹

Nutritional and Lifestyle Recommendations

Small, frequent meals with balanced macronutrient distribution can help stabilize energy levels. The patient is advised against strict diets or rapid weight loss, given their history of worsening neuropsychiatric symptoms post-dieting. Moderate physical activity, such as a 20-30 minute leisurely walk, is recommended to avoid overexertion. Intense exercises like push-ups should be minimized to prevent excessive lactate production and subsequent energy deficits.¹¹

Catecholamine Suppression

The only effective method to prevent potentially life-threatening episodes due to unregulated catecholamine surges involves the use of alpha and beta-blockers, benzodiazepines, and mild opioids. These medications play a crucial role in managing the patient's condition by controlling the excessive catecholamine activity, thus reducing the risk of quite severe metabolic and neuropsychiatric complications.^{17,18}

Conclusion

The patient's complex interplay of cardiac dysfunction, metabolic dysregulation, and autonomic imbalance requires a multifaceted management approach. Continuous monitoring, careful dietary planning, appropriate physical activity, and effective catecholamine suppression are crucial to maintaining metabolic stability and improving quality of life. Further interdisciplinary collaboration and ongoing evaluation are essential to address the evolving needs of Oshtoran Syndrome patients

Conflicts of interest

none

References

1. Castiella A, Urreta I, Zapata E, de Juan MD, Emparanza JI; Burnia Group. H63/H63D genotype and the H63D allele are associated in patients with hyperferritinemia to the development of metabolic syndrome. *Eur J Intern Med.* 2020 Feb;72:106-107. doi: 10.1016/j.ejim.2019.11.021. Epub 2019 Nov 30. PMID: 31796245.
2. Castiella A, Urreta I, Zapata E, de Juan MD, Emparanza JI; Burnia Group. H63/H63D genotype and the H63D allele are associated in patients with hyperferritinemia to the development of metabolic syndrome. *Eur J Intern Med.* 2020 Feb;72:106-107. doi: 10.1016/j.ejim.2019.11.021. Epub 2019 Nov 30. PMID: 31796245.
3. Barut G, Balci H, Bozdayi M, Hatemi I, Ozelik D, Senturk H. Screening for iron overload in the Turkish population. *Dig Dis.* 2003;21(3):279-85. doi: 10.1159/000073985. PMID: 14571105.
4. Diamandis, Carolina, et al. "Oshtoran Syndrome (H63D Syndrome Type-3)." *Authorea Preprints* (2023).
5. Feldman, Jo, et al. "Oshtoran Syndrome aka Spider-Man's Disease or PANS-H63D-Instability-Syndrome: A rare illness amplified by pop culture and scientific perseverance." *Zenodo openAir: Vol* (2023).
6. Diamandis, Carolina, et al. "H63D syndrome (Oslo Syndrome) is clinically the iron sibling of Wilson's disease." *Authorea Preprints* (2022).
7. Pageot C, Bezin J, Smith A, Arnaud M, Salvo F, Haramburu F, Bégaud B, Pariente A; French Network of Pharmacovigilance Centres. Impact of Medicine Withdrawal on Reporting of Adverse Events Involving Therapeutic Alternatives: A Study from the French Spontaneous Reporting Database. *Drug Saf.* 2017 Nov;40(11):1099-1107. doi: 10.1007/s40264-017-0561-y. PMID: 28664354.
8. Papadopoulos, Anastasios, et al. "Prevalence of Narcolepsy in Patients with H63D syndrome." *Available at SSRN 3847055* (2021)
9. Andreeff M, Mono G, Kohn R, Kuhn E. Herzbeteiligung bei Hämochromatose [Heart involvement in hemochromatosis]. *Verh Dtsch Ges Inn Med.* 1971;77:436-8. German. PMID: 4265150.
10. Hauser SC. Hemochromatosis and the heart. *Heart Dis Stroke.* 1993 Nov-Dec;2(6):487-91. PMID: 8137055.
11. Unpublished data
12. Ker J. Hemochromatosis and the heart--heavier than iron? *Int J Card.* 2014 Jan 1;170(3):e70-1. doi: 10.1016/j.ijcard.2013.11.024. Epub 2013 Nov 21. PMID: 24331117
13. Bhandary S, Aguan K. Pyruvate dehydrogenase complex deficiency and its relationship with

epilepsy frequency--An overview. *Epilepsy Res.* 2015 Oct;116:40-52. doi: 10.1016/j.eplesyres.2015.07.002. Epub 2015 Jul 8. PMID: 26354166

14. Oliveira AR, Valente R, Ramos J, Ventura L. Persistent hyperlactacidaemia: about a clinical case. *BMJ Case Rep.* 2013 May 22;2013:bcr2013009485. doi: 10.1136/bcr-2013-009485. PMID: 23704442; PMCID: PMC3670015
15. Mittal R, Debs LH, Patel AP, Nguyen D, Patel K, O'Connor G, Grati M, Mittal J, Yan D, Eshraghi AA, Deo SK, Daunert S, Liu XZ. Neurotransmitters: The Critical Modulators Regulating Gut-Brain Axis. *J Cell Physiol.* 2017 Sep;232(9):2359-2372. doi: 10.1002/jcp.25518. Epub 2017 Apr 10. PMID: 27512962; PMCID: PMC5772764
16. Cramb KML, Beccano-Kelly D, Cragg SJ, Wade-Martins R. Impaired dopamine release in Parkinson's disease. *Brain.* 2023 Aug 1;146(8):3117-3132. doi: 10.1093/brain/awad064. PMID: 36864664; PMCID: PMC10393405
17. Russell, D. C. "Metabolic aspects of cardiac arrhythmias." *Current Opinion in Cardiology* 2.1 (1987): 63-69
18. Iliopoulos, Ilias, Christin Huff, and Eric M. Graham. "Endocrine function in critical heart disease." *Critical Heart Disease in Infants and Children.* Elsevier, 2019. 186-191.

www.swabian.org